

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 2.5 Support for the CCUS Forum

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordinated and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

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SUPPORT FOR THE CCUS FORUM

The CCUS Forum is the European Commission's (EC) main vehicle for the development and deployment of CCS and CCU in the EU. To prepare for the 2022 CCUS Forum in Oslo on 27-28 October, the EC set up three working groups, to focus on 1) a CCUS Vision, 2) CO₂ transport and Storage infrastructure, and 3) Industrial partnership.

ZEP was by the EC given the role of co-chairing working groups 2 and 3. For the working group on CO₂ transport and Storage infrastructure, a working group of some 130 CCS and CCU stakeholder was formed and co-chaired by ZEP, the IOGP and Bellona Europa. An issue paper was prepared on how to develop the European CO₂ infrastructure – 'Towards a European cross-border CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure: Issue paper from the CCUS Forum Working Group on CO₂ Infrastructure'. ZEP has led the work of drafting the paper, that was approved at the CCUS Forum in Oslo.

**Towards a European cross-border CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure:
Issue paper from the CCUS Forum Working Group
on CO₂ Infrastructure**

The final report from the CCUS Forum working group
on CO₂ infrastructure will be published end-February 2023

13 December 2022

Executive summary

Reducing emissions by 2030 and reaching net-zero by 2050 is the main objective of EU climate action and the most important global challenge. There is evidence that carbon capture and storage (CCS) and some applications of carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) can effectively contribute to mitigation efforts. These technologies are crucial for the decarbonisation of industry, in particular the harder-to-abate sectors – and enable carbon dioxide removal (negative emissions), which can balance out residual emissions – contributing to economic growth, sustaining current jobs, and creating new ones.

Recent developments in the CO₂ transport and storage sectors testify to the strong momentum for CCUS in Europe. While industry is ready to deploy, political support has not always been sufficient, leading to uncertainty and delays. At the same time, technical, regulatory, and economic challenges still hinder the development and scale-up of CCUS in Europe.

We welcome the establishment of the CCUS Forum which, through the newly established working groups, can identify the actions that are urgently needed to support the CCUS industry. This issue paper identifies and describes the key technical, regulatory, and economic challenges to the development of a robust, non-discriminatory, open-access, cross-border CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure in Europe. It is critical that the European Commission responds to this issue paper with concrete measures, supporting European global leadership in innovative low-carbon technologies, in line with the objective to be the first climate-neutral continent by 2050.

The key findings and recommendations of this issue paper can be summarised as follows:

- From a technical perspective there is a need for standardisation of CO₂ specifications, addressing the different technologies and segments of the CCUS value chain, including ship-based CCS. This will be critical in supporting interconnections as well as cost efficient deployment of new infrastructure.
- Harmonisation of CO₂ specifications should always be tested for cost effectiveness and considering different CO₂ applications.
- Limited access to information has been highlighted as a barrier to storage appraisal and characterisation. Access to crucial (non-confidential) information for site appraisal must be facilitated so as to support the development of storage sites in Europe. This must be an integral part of a European Storage Atlas.
- To enable large-scale development of CO₂ transport networks in Europe, the legal basis for the export of CO₂ for offshore storage must be further clarified.
- The commercial deployment of CCUS depends on contracts between entities operating along the CCUS value chain, such as emitters, transport companies, and storage and utilisation operators which calls for a proper allocation of liabilities across the CO₂ value chain. Moreover, risk-sharing and transfer of liabilities between the storage developers and the regulatory authorities – as well as transparency regarding this – is key to support project development.
- There is an urgent need for a fit-for-purpose EU regulatory framework for CO₂ transport infrastructure, focused on the development of non-discriminatory, open access and multi-modal CO₂ transport infrastructure while not establishing barriers to early investment. Such a framework would complement Directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of CO₂ (hereinafter ‘CO₂ Storage Directive’).

- Efficient permitting processes and ensuring sufficient number of permitting and licensing rounds are important
- There is limited guidance regarding transfer from oil & gas operations to CO₂ storage operations in hydrocarbon fields. There is also a need for clarity about converting producing hydrocarbon fields to CO₂ storage reservoirs.
- Early engagement between competent authorities and project promoters is essential. Moreover, [ongoing interactions and discussions between project operators and competent authorities are vital to the success of CCUS projects.](#)
- The successful deployment of CCUS at scale will depend on the ability to put in place contracts which balance risks and rewards between the business entities along the CCUS value chain and de-risk the needed investments.
- Funding opportunities should be revised to avoid ‘chicken and egg’ challenges along the CCUS value chain and take into account the need to increase CO₂ storage capacity.

It should be noted that experience is and will continue to evolve with early CCUS projects. These projects will allow the identification of new challenges/barriers and it is important that the EC keeps engaging with industry players to create favourable conditions for the development and operation of CCS and CCU projects, along with research and innovation (R&I). Similarly, different initiatives and programmes that are already in place should be reviewed as a way to identify possible learnings and best practices.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope

The objective of this issue paper, and of the full report that will follow, is to provide clear recommendations to the European Commission (EC) on how to sustainably develop and deploy European CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure to reach climate neutrality by 2050. In this context, the paper identifies key challenges to be addressed to enable the development of an integrated CO₂ network from a regulatory perspective.

The paper focuses on the CO₂ transport and storage components of the value chain (and not on capture), highlighting their technical, regulatory and economic dimensions. Recognising the efficiency gains of developing broad CO₂ markets, the paper takes a wider European perspective, rather than focusing only on EU Member States.

This issue paper (and the full report to follow) does not attempt to describe, in detail, the challenges faced by each individual CCUS technology. Similarly, it is recognised that compared to carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon dioxide removal (CDR), carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) solutions involve more complex value chains, with implications for the planning of transport infrastructure. Nevertheless, all CO₂ flows – CCS, CDR, CCU etc. – need to be taken into account in infrastructure planning and development, which calls for continued investigation into the challenges and needs of different technologies. In addition, at the basis of infrastructure development must be a rigorous assessment of the contribution of the different technologies/projects to climate change mitigation, based on best available scientific evidence, a full life-cycle assessment (including energy use and end-of-life) and thorough carbon accounting, scalability potential within a relevant timeline, and relevance compared to counterfactual scenarios. Similarly, environmental and energy efficiency principles are to be preserved, ensuring that infrastructure development promotes the most efficient solutions for climate neutrality.

The working group (WG) on CO₂ infrastructure urges the EC to respond to this issue paper with concrete action, by filling in the policy gaps and by addressing the technical and economic constraints that are hindering development and scale-up of CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure.

1.2 Work process

The issue paper is developed by the WG on CO₂ infrastructure, based on discussions and input received from a broad membership, including stakeholders from industry, energy, researchers, and environmental NGOs, as well as on existing work that reflects information and research (e.g., reports, studies). The WG has had four meetings between July and November 2022 and benefited from active and fruitful participation, reflecting the urgency of sustainably developing and scaling up CCUS in Europe.

The issue paper should be seen as an integral part of the work conducted under the three CCUS Forum WGs, engaged by the EC. Notably, the WG on CO₂ infrastructure has coordinated with the WG CCUS Vision paper and provided the input on transport and storage that will be included in the Vision paper.

Following the CCUS Forum Plenary (27-28 October), the WG will focus on the preparation of a full report for Q1 2023. An expert group will be established to work on the technical components (e.g. CO₂

specifications). The WG will also provide input to the EC technical and regulatory studies on CO₂ infrastructure and can give input to the review of the CO₂ Storage Directive's Guidance Documents.

1.3 Statement of the challenge

Reducing emissions by 2030 and reaching net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 is the main objective of EU climate action and the most important global challenge. To achieve these objectives, urgent actions must be implemented, based on clear scientific evidence about the role of the different technology solutions. There is evidence that CCS can contribute to significantly reduce carbon emissions into atmosphere and is needed in the majority of scenarios to reach net zero emissions. Some CCU applications can effectively contribute to mitigation¹.

The findings of the 6th Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) working group III² show that:

- “CCS is an option to reduce emissions from large-scale fossil-based energy and industry sources, provided geological storage is available. When CO₂ is captured directly from the atmosphere (DACCS), or from biomass (BECCS), CCS provides the storage component of these CDR methods”
- “The deployment of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) to counterbalance hard-to-abate residual emissions is unavoidable if net zero CO₂ or GHG emissions are to be achieved. (...) CDR refers to anthropogenic activities that remove CO₂ from the atmosphere and store it durably in geological, terrestrial, or ocean reservoirs, or in products”
- “Reducing emissions from the production and use of chemicals would need to rely on a life cycle approach, including (...) carbon sourced through biogenic sources, and, depending on availability, carbon capture and use (CCU), direct air CO₂ capture, as well as CCS”.

Europe benefits from favourable conditions for CO₂ storage. While the storage potential is extremely large, Europe still needs to realise projects to meet the predicted demand from emitters³. The European Commission foresees that 30 projects in preparation will be able to store approximately 50 million tonnes per year by 2030 but emphasises that reaching climate neutrality will require at least six times more CO₂ to be stored per year by 2050⁴. Recent developments are encouraging with the Denmark⁵ and the United Kingdom^{6,7} recently launching its first tenders of CO₂ storage licenses in the North Sea, including both saline aquifers and depleted oil & gas fields. The Norwegian Petroleum Directorate has recently offered

¹ For a revision of the role of CCS and CCU in the EU decarbonisation scenarios, see: Butnar, I., Cronin, J., & Pye, S. (2020). [Review of Carbon Capture Utilisation and Carbon Capture and Storage in future EU decarbonisation scenarios](#). UCL Energy Institute (part of the CCUS SET-Plan Implementation Plan work).

² Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (2022). [Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change](#).

³ Clean Air Task Force (2022). [The gap between carbon storage development and capture demand](#).

⁴ Presentations by DG CLIMA regarding the Innovation Fund and the Projects of Common Interest.

⁵ Danish Energy Agency (2022). [Very first tender of CO₂ storage licenses is opening](#).

⁶ North Sea Transition Authority (2022). [Bids invited in UK's first-ever carbon storage licensing round](#).

⁷ North Sea Transition Authority (2022). [Carbon storage licensing round attracts 26 bids](#).

Wintershall and CapeOmega offered an exploration license for CO₂ storage in the North Sea⁸. Furthermore, the world's first open-source CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure, Northern Lights⁹ is expected to be online by 2025 and is being built ready for expansion to accommodate increasing storage demands. In the Netherlands, the Aramis project¹⁰ will allow several CO₂ storage sites to connect to its offshore transport backbone.

Developments in CO₂ storage infrastructure can also be seen in regions other than the North Sea. Recent project developments in the Mediterranean, the Baltic, and the Black Sea lay the ground for significant offshore storage capacity in the rest of Europe. Furthermore, smaller, but still relevant onshore project initiatives are evolving and are expected to facilitate CO₂ abatement in landlocked regions.

Nevertheless, limited progress in storage development translates into difficulties for capture projects. Notably, identifying storage options has been highlighted as a key hurdle for Innovation Fund projects.

Referring to CO₂ utilisation, the nova-institute has estimated that the global need for embedded carbon in chemicals and derived materials will increase to 1 Gt per year by 2050¹¹. nova-institute further states that sharing, reusing, and recycling will play the main role in keeping carbon in a closed loop. The report adds that, as it is not possible to keep the entire carbon in a cycle, there is a need for alternative carbon sources that can be partially covered by CO₂. Rigorous carbon accounting is a prerequisite when determining any technology's contribution to emission reduction.

The North Sea region benefits from neighbouring European industrial regions and ports such as Aberdeenshire, Amsterdam, Antwerp-Bruges, Dunkirk, Le Havre, Nord-Pas-de-Calais, Rotterdam, Ruhr, the UK East Coast, and Wilhelmshaven. In recent months there has been a positive momentum for European CO₂ infrastructure projects with several key announcements, including an offshore pipeline 'heads of agreement' between Equinor and Wintershall Dea¹² to connect Germany and Norway, a new 1,000 km onshore pipeline project by OGE in Germany¹³ to connect industries to the port of Wilhelmshaven, and 'heads of agreement' between Equinor and Fluxys to connect Belgium and Norway through an offshore pipeline¹⁴.

This momentum will need to be preserved and enhanced through conducive regulatory conditions and EU and national/multilateral funding programmes. While the industry is ready to deploy, there is an urgent need to put in place a robust, non-discriminatory, open-access, cross-border CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure that enables emitters to connect to sinks, as and where needed. In addition, the development of full-scale commercial projects will require all parts of the value chain to be operational

⁸ Norwegian Petroleum Directorate (2022). [Licenses for carbon storage: 2022](#).

⁹ Northern Lights (2022). [Major milestone for decarbonising Europe](#).

¹⁰ TotalEnergies (2021). [Netherlands: TotalEnergies, Shell Netherlands, EBN and Gasunie Form Partnership to Develop the Offshore Aramis CO₂ Transport and Sequestration Project](#).

¹¹ Kähler, F., Carus, M., Porc, O. & vom Berg, C. (2021). [Turning off the Tap for Fossil Carbon – Future Prospects for a Global Chemical and Derived Material Sector Based on Renewable Carbon](#). nova-Institute (Ed.), Hürth, Germany.

¹² Wintershall Dea (2022). [Wintershall Dea and Equinor partner up for large-scale CCS value chain in the North Sea](#).

¹³ OGE (2022). [OGE and TES join forces to develop a 1,000 km CO₂ transmission system](#).

¹⁴ Fluxys (2022). [Fluxys and Equinor launch solution for large-scale decarbonisation in North-Western Europe](#).

which implies that the different components must be developed and implemented in tandem so that capture facilities can be confident that transport and storage facilities will be available and vice versa.

A robust CO₂ infrastructure network is key to enable the development of low-carbon and competitive industrial sectors, provide clean flexibility to the energy sector, and allow to unlock early large-scale volumes of low-carbon hydrogen and carbon dioxide removals. This integration implies that CO₂ infrastructure needs to be developed in parallel and in alignment with the necessary expansion of hydrogen and renewable energy infrastructure. Ports need to be equipped with means for handling CO₂ captured from exhaust gases of ships and need to be integrated into the CO₂ infrastructure to enable effective access to storage sites. Moreover, a CO₂ transport network can enable the supply of necessary CO₂ raw materials, for example, for the chemicals industry.

1.4 International perspective

The Communication on Sustainable Carbon Cycles published by the EC in December 2021¹⁵ highlights the ambition to make the EU a leader in innovative low-carbon technologies and in CCUS, putting forward several proposals to create an internal market for capture, use, and storage of CO₂, supported by an open-access and cross-border transport network. At the same time, important political developments at the international level are bringing unprecedented support to CCUS technologies. For instance, in August 2022, President Joe Biden signed the Inflation Reduction Act, increasing the already available tax credits (known as 45Q) for CCS and CCU from DAC. While this represents a positive signal for the global development of CCUS, it should at the same time call on Europe to raise its support to unlock its potential to build industrial, economic, and political leadership in innovative low-carbon technologies in line with the objective to be the first climate-neutral continent by 2050.

¹⁵ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council Sustainable Carbon Cycles, December 2021 ([here](#)).

2 THE STRUCTURE OF THE CO₂ INFRASTRUCTURE MARKET

The current legal basis for the storage of CO₂ in Europe is the Directive 2009/31 on the Geological Storage of carbon dioxide ('CO₂ Storage Directive')¹⁶. The Directive includes provisions on site selection and characterisation, conditions for permitting, as well as monitoring and reporting requirements to verify storage, including remediation obligations in case of failures. It also includes some requirements on providing third-party access to infrastructure. The EC publishes biannually reports on the implementation of Directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of CO₂ (hereinafter 'CO₂ Storage Directive')¹⁷ which highlights progress in EU Member States.

Experience with storage permit applications in the Member States and at EU level is currently evolving under the directive and its Guidance Documents. A review of the Guidance Documents is set to start in December 2022, with publication intended in 2023. There is a clear consensus that the directive itself should not be opened for review, however, some elements of the Guidance Documents could benefit from an update as highlighted in a recent ZEP report¹⁸.

Some elements of the CO₂ Storage Directive cover CO₂ transport and the TEN-E regulation focuses on CO₂ infrastructure development in a bottom-up process, via the development of projects of common interest (PCI); nonetheless, the development of an overarching regulatory framework for CO₂ transport will be needed. A fit-for-purpose regulatory framework for CO₂ transport, which supports non-discriminatory, open-access, multimodal CO₂ transport infrastructure, would establish a clear legal and regulatory basis for planned projects, in particular for cross-border cooperation, and would enable coordinated CO₂ infrastructure planning, regional cooperation and harmonised standards on the transport part of the CCUS value chain (e.g., Monitoring Reporting and Verification, CO₂ quality specifications), in line with the CO₂ Storage Directive and the Monitoring and Reporting Regulation.

As noted above, most large-scale geological storage projects are currently concentrated in the North Sea, while CO₂ emitters are widely spread across Europe, including in hinterland areas far from the coast. Thus, there is a crucial need for European CO₂ transport infrastructure to connect dispersed emitters across Europe to storage facilities.

While technologies have reached a stage of maturity that allows the value chain to be implemented and operated, there are remaining challenges that can hinder the scale-up of CCUS to the levels that are needed for decarbonisation. The following chapters assess the main technical, regulatory and economic challenges faced by CO₂ transport and storage operators and proposes possible solutions. Importantly, while this issue paper sought to be forward looking, it is true that experience is and will evolve with the ongoing and soon to start CCS and CCU projects. These projects will allow the identification of new challenges/barriers and it is important that the EC keeps engaging with industry actors to create favourable

¹⁶ Directive 2009/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the geological storage of carbon dioxide and amending Council Directive 85/337/EEC, European Parliament and Council Directives 2000/60/EC, 2001/80/EC, 2004/35/EC, 2006/12/EC, 2008/1/EC and Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 (Text with EEA relevance) ([here](#)).

¹⁷ Reports on the implementation of the CO₂ Storage Directive ([here](#)).

¹⁸ Zero Emissions Platform (2022). [Experience in developing CO₂ storage under the Directive on the geological storage of carbon dioxide](#).

conditions for the development and operation of CCS and CCU projects. Similarly, there is some experience on how to deal with some of the technical, regulatory, and economic issues identified. The different initiatives and programmes that are already in place should be reviewed as a way to identify possible learnings and best practices.

3 TECHNICAL DIMENSION

This chapter presents the main technical barriers to large-scale deployment, focusing on the transport and storage components of the value chain¹⁹.

3.1 Transport

CCUS projects, both cross-border and domestic, will rely on different modalities for the transport of CO₂ such as pipelines, rail, ships, barges, and trucks. While most of the CO₂ transport is currently done via pipeline, the role of CO₂ transport by ship will become equally important – both maritime and inland rivers and canals. CO₂ transport by ship will be crucial to the operationalisation of CCUS PCIs²⁰.

The transport of CO₂ in a multi-modal, multi-origin, cross-border, fit-for-purpose and flexible open-access network will present technical challenges, as it will require handling CO₂ streams from different technologies and different sources²¹. Although initial transport projects and contracts will likely be between a given emitter and a specific sink, there is a need for standardisation of CO₂ specifications (gaseous and liquid), taking into account the different technologies and addressing matters such as composition, purity, pressures and temperatures, as well as standards for the design of pipelines, valves, ships, and other parts of the transport value chain (e.g., loading and off-loading). This will support interoperability and interconnections across Europe, across national borders and different transport modalities. As highlighted in a recent report²², given the similarity between CO₂ phase behaviour and Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG), existing standards for transport of LPG by ship can be a good starting point for liquified CO₂ and, potentially, for dual use shipping. Global standards are relevant for the application of CCS technologies to the exhaust gases of ships, which need to be able to unload captured CO₂ in ports all over the world.

Developing CO₂ transport networks will also involve dealing with complex issues such as liabilities for transport owners / operators, requiring entry/exit tracing of CO₂ sources and composition, as they account for a substantial proportion of global CO₂ emissions.

The development of CO₂ transport networks must consider connections to small and stranded emitters (i.e., emitters that are distant from CCUS/industrial clusters), as they account for a substantial proportion of global CO₂ emissions. As a direct connection to pipeline infrastructure may not be feasible for these emitters, viable alternatives can involve transporting CO₂ via low-pressure pipelines, truck or rail. While processing these CO₂ streams at central hubs (clusters) is likely to be an economically attractive option for small emitters and for CO₂ captured on board of ships, it also increases the transport challenges due to varying levels of impurities which leads to more complex phase behaviour of the unprocessed CO₂.

¹⁹ This chapter draws on findings by the CCUS SET-Plan Implementation Plan work (2020/21): [Report on key enablers and hurdles impacting on CCUS deployment with an assessment of current activities to address these issues](#), and [CCUS Roadmap to 2030](#).

²⁰ CCUS SET-Plan Implementation Plan (2022): [Recommendations on the steps required to deliver the R&I activities 3: EU Projects of Common Interest for CO₂ transport infrastructure](#).

²¹ Zero Emissions Platform (2020). [A Trans-European CO₂ Transportation Infrastructure for CCUS: Opportunities & Challenges](#).

²² Zero Emissions Platform & Carbon Capture and Storage Association (2022). [Guidance for CO₂ transport by ship](#).

3.2 Storage

This section describes current challenges regarding CO₂ storage, focusing in particular on:

- The types of storages
- The potential for CO₂ storage in Europe
- The stages of a typical CO₂ storage development process

Figure 1 - Countries where CO₂ storage is permitted and prohibited. Source: CO₂GeoNet (2021). [State-of-play on CO₂ geological storage in 32 European countries — an update.](#)

The types of storages

Different types of on- and offshore storage sites exist such as depleted oil & gas fields and saline aquifers, with different characteristics, risk profiles, availability and implications for the regulatory framework. It is important that these implications are duly considered.

Deep saline formations or saline aquifers are expected to offer the largest CO₂ storage capacity²³. These options are being explored in the North Sea, where Sleipner, Snøhvit, Longship, the UK East Coast Cluster and ACORN are either storing or planning to store CO₂ in saline aquifers.

Depleted oil & gas fields, especially in the North Sea have been appraised by oil & gas operators and can be viable solutions to store large quantities of CO₂. Offshore storage is particularly suitable for countries where onshore storage is banned or may encounter public acceptance issues with onshore storage. In many European countries, mainly in the central, eastern, and south-eastern part of the continent, depleted and nearly depleted onshore oil&gas fields can offer early CO₂ storage solutions. The potential use of existing wells and surface facilities also presents cost saving opportunities for storage developers.

The potential for CO₂ storage in Europe, site appraisal and characterisation

While there is no lack of potential for CO₂ storage in Europe, significant investments decisions are needed to make this potential marketable storage capacities. At the technical level, this involves supporting prospective storage promoters to swiftly identify suitable storage sites.

The limited access to information has also been highlighted as a key barrier in site appraisal and characterisation. Thus, there is a need for competent authorities to outline a pathway that enables the future storage operator to access non-confidential information required to undertake site appraisal activities (e.g., re-use of wells, well maintenance records, annulus pressure data, reservoir performance etc.).

²³ Global CCS Institute (2022). [Global Status of CCS 2022.](#)

While it is outside the scope of this work to identify a single best option to access crucial information for site appraisal, it is noted that this would benefit the development of storage sites in Europe and should be an integral part of a European Storage Atlas²⁴, to support investment decisions. The CO₂StoP database²⁵ provides pan-European coverage of CO₂ storage potential; however, as highlighted by a recent CO₂GeoNet report²⁶, new storage assessments and new data have become available in at least 25 European countries since preparation of the database and an updated and maintained European Storage Atlas would enable CCS project developers to identify storage resources for further appraisal and prepare for the development of larger storage capacities²⁷.

It is also noted that various attempts have been made to classify storage capacities and to understand the remaining actions that are required to advance from storage potential to stored CO₂. For example, the SPE SRMS²⁸ aims to classify storage resources in terms of readiness for investment following the approach taken by the oil and gas industry. The UNECE UNFC approach application to injection projects²⁹ classifies the maturity of an injection project considering economic and social viability, field project status and feasibility, and geological knowledge.

The stages of a typical CO₂ storage project

Storage development is a prerequisite of the value chain and is on average more time consuming in development than capture. A storage project may take 10 years to mature up from inception to the point of injection. Liability is the basis for the many steps of CO₂ storage development: identification of storage sites, exploration and appraisal, licensing of storage sites, signing up of emitters, securing transport and storage becoming operational³⁰. Moreover, it is important to take into account site closure, including a clear understanding of regulatory and financial barriers.

²⁴ The 'Storage Atlas' concept is further developed in the CCUS SET-Plan Implementation Plan work (2022): [Recommendations on the steps to establish a R&I Activity 4 European Storage Atlas](#).

²⁵ More information and maps with geological data can be accessed [here](#).

²⁶ CO₂GeoNet (2021). [State-of-play on CO₂ geological storage in 32 European countries - an update](#).

²⁷ For more information on storage appraisal, see: Unlocking European CO₂ storage capacity: recommendations on the steps required to deliver target 7 of the SET Plan's Implementation Working Group on CCS and CCU (2022).

²⁸ CO₂ Storage Resources Management System. Available [here](#).

²⁹ More information about the UNFC system and UNFC documents available [here](#).

³⁰ For an overview of the regulatory landscape on CO₂ storage, see: Zero Emissions Platform (2022). [Experience in developing CO₂ storage under the Directive on the geological storage of carbon dioxide](#).

4 REGULATORY DIMENSION

A stable policy and regulatory framework is key for the large-scale development of CCS and CCU within this decade. While industry is ready to deploy, the political support for the technology has not always been sufficient, leading to uncertainty and delays.

To support the development of CO₂ networks in an environmentally safe and secure manner, a best-available-technology approach (relevant to the risks associated with CO₂) is required (regulated by the Paris Agreement and the UNFCCC). Moreover, contracts between emitters, transport owners and operators, and storage and utilisation operators need to ensure a proper allocation of liabilities across the CO₂ value chain and tracking of CO₂ volumes in line with the EU ETS Directive and the Monitoring and Reporting Regulation. Further assessment of options for allocation and management of liabilities and financial guarantees is already in place.

Cross-border transport of CO₂ for offshore storage is regulated under the London Protocol of the International Maritime Organisation (IMO), namely, Article 6. Since 2019, a provisional solution (i.e., pending entry into force of the 2009 amendment to Article 6) allows CO₂ export for sub-seabed storage for countries that enter into bilateral IMO agreements. In the European Economic Area (EEA), a simplified process – with a notification to the IMO but no bilateral agreements needed – may apply, according to a recent analysis paper³¹ published by DG CLIMA. However, to enable large-scale development of CO₂ transport networks in Europe, the legal status and implications of the analysis paper must be clarified. Furthermore, incentives to ratify the 2009 amendment must be maintained, allowing its entry into force and enable CO₂ cross-border flows for offshore storage, also connecting countries outside of the EEA.

Moreover, the legal frameworks should enable the development of a competitive and efficient market taking all of Europe into account. As described above, the EU has ample storage potential. Building partnerships with EEA countries would also bring about a number of benefits. Moreover, the UK part of the North Sea has a large potential for CO₂ storage that can be an alternative competitive option for emitters in the EEA. In this context, the recognition of CO₂ exported to the UK for permanent storage under the EU ETS system (and vice versa) would facilitate CO₂ flows between the EU and the UK and unlock access to competitive storage options for emitters. The above-mentioned analysis paper maintains that the exception to surrendering emission allowances does not apply to EU ETS installations that export CO₂ for storage outside the EEA (e.g. the UK). Such a legal landscape could effectively create an obstacle to the development of a wider (European) market for CO₂ transport and storage.

4.1 Transport

As stated in previous chapters, to enable the development of CCUS at large scale in Europe, the EC should develop a regulatory framework for CO₂ transport infrastructure, focused on the development of non-discriminatory, open access and multi-modal CO₂ transport infrastructure³². Such a regulatory framework

³¹ Commission services analysis paper for the Information Exchange Group (IEG) under Directive 2009/31/EC. Available [here](#).

³² Zero Emissions Platform (2021). [ZEP proposal for a regulatory framework for CO2 transport infrastructure](#)

would complement the CO₂ Storage Directive and establish a legal and regulatory basis for planned projects, notably the cross-border CO₂ PCIs which are on track to become operational before 2025. A robust policy framework providing a degree of predictability for long-term investments and creating a competitive environment for operators should be a priority for European policymakers.

CO₂ infrastructure projects call on European legislators to extend the scope of existing legislation – such as the TEN-E regulation, TEN-T Regulation and EU ETS Directive – to prepare for the rollout of large-scale, shared CO₂ infrastructure. The EU Taxonomy recognises all modes of CO₂ transportation – pipeline, ship, barge, rail, truck. This outcome is critical and should be preserved and reflected in all revised relevant legislation, as it will allow near-ready CO₂ transport and storage projects to be realised and to create opportunities for numerous CO₂ emitters throughout the EU/EEA area to have access to low-cost decarbonisation pathways.

A regulatory framework should include the following elements

- *CO₂ infrastructure network operator*
 Deployment of new CO₂ transport corridors and networks would benefit from integrated planning and consultation processes, in a similar way to those established for the gas, electricity and hydrogen sectors (ENTSO-E, ENTSO-G and ENNOH, respectively). An equivalent entity for CCUS – incorporating emitters, transport providers and utilisation and storage operators and with a mandate to consider value-chain regulatory issues and make recommendations to the EC – would enable coordinated CO₂ infrastructure planning, network design, and facilitate cross-border cooperation, thereby supporting the deployment of new CO₂ networks. This entity could address regulatory and permitting barriers and promote relevant standardisation across the value chain, including on CO₂ quality specifications and shipping of CO₂.
- *The CCUS Forum as an EU regulatory and stakeholder forum for CO₂ networks*
 The CCUS Forum can act as the body to take stock of the experience developed under a regulatory framework, in a similar approach to that of the Madrid Forum for Gas and the Florence Forum for Electricity. A joint approach to developing Forum Conclusions can be helpful in achieving transparent alignment on the work programme. The Forum would be well placed to provide recommendations to national and European policy makers, supporting progress on specific regulatory / policy challenges.
- *Integrated network planning*
 An important element under the Hydrogen and Gas Decarbonisation Package proposals is fostering integrated network planning and interaction between the electricity, gas and hydrogen sectors, in order to promote flexibility and resilience in the EU energy system. Work to integrate the role and scope of CO₂ transport infrastructure into energy network development planning, including integrated 10-year network development plans (TYNDP), should be undertaken as part of a regulatory framework for CO₂ transport infrastructure. This scope could cover both localised CO₂ grids (e.g., in coastal areas / ports) and cross-border / regional CO₂ backbone infrastructure.

As established by the TEN-E, network planning shall involve a participatory approach, whereby all relevant stakeholders, including CO₂ infrastructure stakeholders and civil society organisations, are invited to provide input through consultation.

- *Regional cooperation*

A regional approach for discussions around CO₂ infrastructure could trigger more efficient infrastructure cooperation and deployment, with a particular focus on integration between cross-border CCUS systems. Applying this logic for CO₂ infrastructure could be facilitated by the EC and policy makers in Europe, either under the CCUS Forum or as part of any new platform for CO₂ infrastructure, as included in the TEN-E regulation.

Planning and investment in infrastructure can be supported by regional development organisations, functioning as market makers, sitting between industrial CO₂ sources and CO₂ users and stores. Such organisations would coordinate development and take responsibility for risks³³. In essence, they would create a framework to allocate market risks and liabilities between the public and private sector by deploying CO₂ network capacity in line with national and regional strategic industrial decarbonisation plans. These organisations would reduce investment and performance risk by having a mandate to, and develop, a market for CO₂ transport and storage – it would also provide much needed policy certainty to emitters looking to decarbonise. They can also contribute to action by preserving infrastructure, which is about to be decommissioned and dismantled, where it is still strategically useful.

- *Public perception and acceptability*

The development and construction of new long-distance infrastructure often faces challenges regarding public acceptance. Mechanisms and best practices for inviting public consultation and integrating feedback into CO₂ transport infrastructure planning, including the development of guidance on public engagement and support for new and repurposed infrastructure, will be an important element of the broader policy framework and must be integrated into the scope of the CO₂ infrastructure network operator.

- *Flexibility of approach*

Experience in CCUS is evolving, with potential for innovation to drive efficiency, cost reductions and enhance integration. For this reason, regulatory flexibility – while prioritising environmental integrity – must be preserved, such that CO₂ infrastructure providers and operators are not faced with unnecessary complexity and cost that are detrimental to efficient project implementation. The regulatory sandbox approach under the Innovation Fund could serve as a testing ground for approaches that could then be supported more broadly under the regulatory framework for CO₂ transport infrastructure.

Moreover, it is important to ensure that an EU regulatory framework for CO₂ transport does not create barriers for projects that were initiated under a different legislative setting.

- *Supporting delivery of Trans-European Network provisions on CO₂ infrastructure and NECPs*

Recent integration of CO₂ storage into the TEN-E Regulation and incorporation of CCUS in National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) has helped to better support the role of CCUS in achieving decarbonisation targets in Member States and at the EU level. The Hydrogen and Decarbonised Gas Market Package contains provisions to assist Member States with implementation of the hydrogen provisions of TEN-E, as well as supporting delivery of the hydrogen components of the NECPs. Since CO₂ infrastructure is a part of the revised TEN-E regulation as well as a number of NECPs, a similar link

³³ Bellona Europa (2016). [Manufacturing Our Future: Industries, European Regions, and Climate Action.](#)

should be established between the regulatory framework for CO₂ infrastructure and achieving the CCUS elements of the new TEN-E/ NECPs, in order to support successful delivery.

- *Facilitating sharing of best practices at EU level*
The cross-border transport of CO₂ and the coordination of CO₂ streams from different sources brings about technical challenges. Facilitating the sharing of best practices at EU level is needed to address existing differences in technical requirements with regards to the construction and characteristics of pipelines for cross-border pipeline projects.

Standards

Driving a standardised approach in relevant areas of the CCUS value chain will be important in promoting interconnections as well as cost efficient deployment of new infrastructure; the development of standards would thus complement the regulatory framework for the transport of CO₂. ISO TC 265³⁴ includes voluntary standards for CO₂ capture, transportation, and geological storage. Standards for various modalities of transport have been proposed but transport and storage operators have indicated that common standards for CO₂ transport and storage would support the development of shared infrastructure and a European-wide network of potential emitters and sinks.

While providing a full list of standards is outside the scope of this issue paper, areas of potential focus for standards includes CO₂ composition, pressure, purity and temperature as well as for the design of the different components of the transport value chain.

Harmonisation, specifically for CO₂ specifications, should always be tested for cost effectiveness and consider the different CO₂ applications. Existing standardisation bodies are well placed to undertake this work. An assessment of existing standards will be done to identify potential gaps³⁵ leveraging from existing work.

4.2 Storage

As described in the technical section above, different types of on- and offshore storage sites exist such as depleted oil & gas fields and saline aquifers. Their different characteristics, risk profiles, and availability must be duly considered under the regulatory framework as which they may lead to different criteria, risks, and timelines when developing storage.

Regulatory challenges related to storage concern both EU and national legal frameworks. The following paragraphs describe the challenges that have been identified and reflect the evidence gathered in a recent ZEP report³⁶.

Permitting processes tend to be quite lengthy and complex in most EU member states, usually taking between 18 months and 2 years (compared to 6 to 9 months in the UK). Besides providing guidelines to

³⁴ More information and ISO documents available [here](#).

³⁵ e.g. IOGP is conducting an Analysis of Standards & Guides addressing Carbon Capture, Transport and Storage, which will be made available as soon as finalised.

³⁶ Zero Emissions Platform (2022). [Experience in developing CO₂ storage under the Directive on the geological storage of carbon dioxide](#).

speed up permitting – while maintaining environmental safeguards –, the EU can improve the current permitting procedures by striving to provide a timely opinion for Member States' licensing decisions. Moreover, a limited number of permitting and licensing rounds have been carried out.

Limited guidance regarding transfer from oil & gas operations to CO₂ storage operations in hydrocarbon fields. There might be an incompatibility between operator's preference for rapid removal of an oil and gas platform, due to high maintenance costs, and the desire to adapt multiple platforms and wells for CO₂ storage service in an orderly manner. Notably, guidance on transfer of liabilities as well as on the role of the different actors (competent authorities, owners, and future developers) during the transfer process is needed.

There is also a need for clarity about converting producing hydrocarbon fields to CO₂ storage reservoirs. While early CO₂ storage projects in Europe that use (offshore) depleted hydrocarbon fields as the storage reservoir commence injection after the end of oil or gas production, there may be advantages, especially in merging the tail end of hydrocarbon production with the first phase of CO₂ injection in cases where this is an option. For access to new geological CO₂ storage capacity, it could be helpful to assess the synergies and potential mutual relevance of the EU Hydrocarbons Licensing Directive³⁷ and the CO₂ Storage Directive, supporting access to information and site characterisation, and provide clarity regarding the risk allocation between the oil & gas and storage operators.

Early engagement between Competent Authorities and project promoters is needed to provide clarity (e.g., on the required level of detail in the interim documents/plans, including the criteria for the demonstration of permanent storage which should be agreed with operators on a case -by -case basis) and guidance where needed, avoiding misunderstandings and delays. Moreover, [ongoing interactions and discussions between the project operators and Competent Authorities have been identified as critical to the success of CCUS projects.](#)

With regard to liabilities for storage operators, several countries (including Norway (only the Longship project) and the UK) have developed options that enable risk-sharing and transfer of liabilities between the storage developers and the regulatory authorities. It is crucial to assess how private investors and governments could share long-term CO₂ storage risks. Possible avenues, including the establishment of a national fund for pooled liabilities for storage resources and an international fund to for international transport liabilities could be pursued, creating a post-closure company, insurance systems and robust and independent review of risks and imposition of risk criteria for low-probability incidents.

Financial securities for storage sites can vary considerably depending on the interpretation of regulations and can be particularly prohibitive for smaller operators. The operators should set up insurance schemes that include public and private funding. If that is not possible, the operator should calculate the size of the fund based on a percentile of costs and not on expected values. National governments should have a robust and independent review of the risks and impose risk criteria for low-probability incidents.

The upcoming review of the CO₂ Storage Directive Guidance Documents will offer an opportunity to address these issues and challenges. Moreover, there is an opportunity to share learnings and identify best

³⁷ Directive 94/22/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 1994 on the conditions for granting and using authorizations for the prospection, exploration and production of hydrocarbons. Available [here](#).

practices from permitting procedures that have already been conducted. Building knowledge and capacity within Competent Authorities will also be crucial to streamline CCUS project development.

5 COMMERCIAL MODELS AND CONSIDERATIONS ON FUNDING MECHANISMS

5.1 Commercial models

CCUS value chains typically include multiple separate business entities such as industry emitting, capturing and processing CO₂, infrastructure operators transporting CO₂ (whether through pipelines or by other modes), operators managing interim storage (e.g. ports), entities aggregating CO₂ flows from multiple emitters, CO₂ storage operators and CO₂ users. Successful deployment of CCUS at scale will depend on the ability to put in place commercial solutions that balances risk and reward along the full CCUS value chain, underpinning and de-risking the needed investments.

When developing commercial models and de-risking measures, there are two key commercial risks that should be carefully considered: *price risks* and *volume risks*.

The price (variation) risks

For industries emitting CO₂, the value of capturing, transporting, and storing CO₂ largely depends on the alternative cost of emitting CO₂. The costs of emitting CO₂ have historically been relatively low, (aided by free allocation of EU ETS allowances), and thus not incentivising investment in CO₂ capture. However, they have increased and become more volatile over the past years. De-risking the investment in CO₂ capture suggests the need for business models which can guarantee stable revenue streams over longer time periods, e.g., a possibility for emitters to enter carbon contracts for difference (CCfD) with an entity which can assume the corresponding price risk and guarantee investors stable returns on their investments. Such entity could be at Member State or an EU level.

Companies transporting and/or storing CO₂ typically require some form of longer-term commitment, with tariffs paid for certain agreed capacities, to invest in corresponding transport and/or storage infrastructure (including repurposing of existing infrastructure), whether under regulated or non-regulated terms. The entity that is entering into a contract for the transportation or storage can be an aggregator who receives the CO₂ from emitters for a fee sufficiently high to pay for the transport and storage of CO₂ volumes.

The volume (certainty) risks

CO₂ emitters that wish to invest in CO₂ capture and linked processing facilities will likely require certainty over their ability to dispose of the captured CO₂ over the lifetime of the emitting asset. They will therefore likely require CO₂ off-take commitments from aggregators over a longer time scale, potentially decades. On the other hand, since their activity depends on different external economic drivers outside of their own control, emitters may not possess the certainty to guarantee the supply of captured CO₂ over a period longer than a few years. This may result in a mismatch, since emitters may be willing to enter into commitments of shorter length than those sought by investors into transportation and storage infrastructure. Entities in the value chain (e.g. an aggregator) that are exposed to this mismatch risk may find the need to establish de-risking mechanisms with external bodies before concluding commercial agreements with emitters, transport companies and/or storage operators.

5.2 Funding mechanisms

Funding mechanism need to address the different commercial risks along the value chain and over the lifetime of CCUS projects. There are already several existing EU funding mechanisms that can contribute to the development of a European CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure network³⁸. It is crucial that these funding mechanisms – and additional funding and de-risking mechanism yet to be established – are coherent and coordinated both across funds and between the EU and Member State levels, for targeted and efficient deployment. Notably, the recently established Just Transition Platform, under the leadership of DG REGIO, which includes working groups relevant to CO₂ infrastructure, can provide a good basis for such coordination.

Existing funding mechanisms and possible improvements

- A separate funding window for CCUS projects in the EU Innovation Fund would simplify the process and avoid timing issues when establishing back-to-back contractual rights and obligations between emitters, transporters and storers. Introducing the possibility of sequenced funding for CCUS projects should be contemplated to address ‘chicken and egg’ challenges – i.e. to provide for the development of CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure such that it is ready for capture projects to use at the required time. This upfront investment in storage can protect large investments in CO₂ capture projects. Given the critical need for CO₂ storage and the experience collected from Innovation Fund calls, the European Commission should assess other funding possibilities, linked directly to increasing CO₂ storage capacity.
- The EU Innovation Fund should also fund CCUS projects through CCfD mechanisms (as proposed in the EU ETS reform). However, Member States must continue to be able to also establish national CCfD models. EU legislation can ensure that overlap between EU and Member State funding is addressed.

Additional funding /de-risking mechanism

- De-risking long term revenue streams for investors along the CCUS value chain beyond the initial CCUS projects phase and thus supporting a fast scale up of a CCUS economy requires measures which address price (variation) risk and volume certainty risks. Tools that can successfully achieve this include CCfDs, private-public partnerships, etc.

Liability risks

- CO₂ and related liabilities need to be clearly defined and clarified across the different entities along the value chain. In particular, it must be ensured that liabilities are transferred once storage operations cease. Uncertainty on liabilities can create commercial risks which consequently increase costs to investors. Referring to the CO₂, liabilities and allowances under the EU ETS must all be aligned, including, where appropriate, the development of optimised or new financial security instruments.

Other funding considerations

- The EC should support cross-border transportation of CO₂ to enable access from emitters in one country to storage sites in another, thereby supporting the fast scaling up of CCUS value chains. Hurdles associated with multi-country funding and/or state aid guidelines should be reviewed and adjusted to allow and facilitate the creation of cross-border value chains.

³⁸ Bellona Europa (2018). [An industry's guide to climate action](#).

- Support learnings from initial projects, for example, by providing incentives for the funding of first-generation infrastructure projects to develop targeted research on open questions so as to support the economics and environmental benefits of next generation infrastructure.
- The development of business models and potential tariffs should reflect the different risks and conditions along the CCUS value chain. For instance, in the case of remote sites it will be important to ensure that the decarbonisation remains possible at an affordable cost for emitters.
- Experience developed with financing tools outside of Europe (e.g. the US the carbon dioxide sequestration credit 45Q) can also provide important insights that can feed into the development of financing mechanisms in Europe.

6 GUIDANCE FOR GOVERNMENTS AND NECP REVISION

This issue paper will provide clear guidance for Member States to include CCUS in National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs). Draft NECPs cover energy and climate plans to 2030³⁹, whereas long term strategies cover the period until 2050⁴⁰. It is notable that CCUS is included in fewer NECPs than long term strategies. Strategic development of European CCUS infrastructure could help bridge this emerging gap between expected need for storage and current CCUS projects⁴¹ and provide the required step change in CCUS deployment. In this context, the working group welcomes the inclusion in the latest Guidance to MS for updated NECPs 2021-2030⁴² of a section recommending to Member States to include in their updated NECPs the efforts planned towards capture and storage of CO₂.

To complement this process, it will be crucial to focus on building capacity at the national, regional, and local level, as well as on awareness raising among national and regional administrations. This should also ensure that the CO₂ Storage Directive is implemented effectively at the national level. The forthcoming update of the guidance documents and the capacity building workshops that are planned for 2024 should also provide a good basis for coordinated implementation.

Raising awareness and understanding of the technology is crucial. The IPCC Sixth Assessment Report, 'Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change' stated that the public is largely unfamiliar with CCUS, and that strong local resistance can contribute to the cancellation of CCS projects.

Limited incentives to accelerate societal support represents another significant risk. Member States, European policymakers and all relevant stakeholders must collaborate to ensure that there is a robust understanding of public perception regarding the development of storage infrastructure and that acceptability is not threatened by false perceptions or confusion. Opposition from local communities represents a legal risk that should be taken into account. Therefore, early engagement with local communities by trusted and reputable entities raising awareness and reinsuring the public on the CCUS technologies could help improve public perception and understanding of CCUS.

³⁹ More information about the NECPs and the Member States' NECPs can be found [here](#).

⁴⁰ More information about the long-term strategies and the Member States' national long-term strategies can be found [here](#).

⁴¹ The Carbon Sequestration Leadership Forum (2021). [2021 Carbon Sequestration Technology Roadmap](#).

⁴² European Commission (2022). [Communication and annex - Guidance to MS for updated NECPs 2021-2030](#).

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Annex 2: Working group members

Members of the CCUS Forum working group on CO₂ infrastructure include stakeholders from industry, energy, utilities, technology and equipment suppliers, researchers, and environmental NGOs. This issue paper benefitted from the active engagement and the input of these various members, who kindly contributed with their useful comments and materials.

Annex 3: Glossary/Definitions

BECCS – Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage refers to the combustion or conversion of biomass with carbon capture and storage applied to the resulting biogenic CO₂. BECCS is a CO₂ removal technology, provided the biomass is sustainably sourced and value chain emissions are accounted for.

CCS – Carbon capture and storage refers to the capture (separation) of carbon dioxide (CO₂) from various sources, followed by its transport and injection into a suitable underground geological formation for the purposes of permanent storage.

CCU – Carbon capture and utilisation is a process in which CO₂ is separated from CO₂ point sources or ambient air and is subsequently used in or as a product.

CCUS – Carbon capture, utilisation and storage encompasses the suite of technologies used to capture, transport, utilise, and store CO₂, including CCU, CCS, BECCS, and DACS, for the purposes of emissions reduction or CO₂ removal from the atmosphere.

CDR – Carbon dioxide removal refers to anthropogenic processes which remove CO₂ from the atmosphere and durably store it in geological, terrestrial, or ocean reservoirs, or in products (also referred to as negative emissions).

Cluster – Multiple carbon dioxide emitters geographically located near each other, sharing CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure.

CO₂ Storage Directive – Directive 2009/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the geological storage of carbon dioxide and amending Council Directive 85/337/EEC, European Parliament and Council Directives 2000/60/EC, 2001/80/EC, 2004/35/EC, 2006/12/EC, 2008/1/EC and Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 (Text with EEA relevance).

DACS – Direct air capture and storage is the separation of CO₂ from ambient air followed by permanent geological storage. DACS is a CO₂ removal technology, provided value chain emissions are accounted for.

LCA – Life cycle assessment, a methodology to evaluate the environmental impacts of a product or process throughout its life cycle.

Open access / third-party access – in accordance with Chapter 5 of the CO₂ Storage Directive, open access or third-party access is here conceptualised as the guarantee that “potential users are able to obtain access to transport networks and to storage sites for the purposes of geological storage of the produced and captured CO₂” and that such access “shall be provided in a transparent and non-discriminatory manner”.

Stranded emitters – Carbon dioxide emitters that are distant from CCUS/industrial clusters, ports, and other CO₂ transport modes.

Technology-based removals – Encompasses technologies such as DACS and BECCS – as opposed to nature-based removals.